

Run14 AuAu EMCAL Geometry Tuning

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Abstract

In this note, we present the adjustments we did for EMCAL geometry used in the reconstruction to ensure a self consistent EMCAL geometry in simulation and data respectively.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Abnormal π^0 peak width in PISA simulation – EMCAL geometry issue

The original plot triggered this EMCAL geometry study is shown in Fig. 1 (a). We generated single π^0 to $\gamma\gamma$ decay in simulation. Since one of the decay γ is forced to convert to e^+e^- pair, this kind of event is later referred as $e^+e^-\gamma$ event. Such event is fed to PISA and then went through the PHENIX reconstruction code used for simulation, which corresponds to the pisaToDST step. During this step, e^\pm are reconstructed as tracks via PHENIX central arm tracking system (e.g. Drift Chamber) while γ are reconstructed as clusters via EMCAL. At the end, our analysis module is applied on the simDST files, and events with e^\pm tracks and γ clusters are saved to a root TTree. For the interest of our analysis, we checked the parent π^0 mass distribution reconstructed from conversion pair (e^+e^- pair) γ cluster channel to see if there is a reasonable π^0 peak. Depending on which sector the γ clusters hit, π^0 peaks are checked respectively. Fig. 1 (a) shows the extracted π^0 peak sigma from a Gaussian fit as a function of $p_T^{\pi^0}$ for all 8 sectors. One can immediately notice one outlier which corresponds to sector E1. When selecting the γ clusters from E1 sector, the π^0 peak width increase dramatically with the $p_T^{\pi^0}$. Fig. 1 (b) shows the reconstructed π^0 mass distribution for a specific $p_T^{\pi^0}$ bin, one can observe a broadened peak structure which corresponds to the increasing peak width seen in Fig. 1 (a). The reason for such broadening of the π^0 peak width is actually due to a misreconstructed γ cluster position. Fig. 1 (c) shows the displacement between the reconstructed γ cluster and the true impact position. If the cluster is reconstructed correctly, we should expect a 2D distribution centered at (0,0), but on the contrary a ~ 0.01 rad offset is observed along azimuthal direction. After further

Figure 1: (a) Extracted π^0 peak sigma (reconstructed from $e^+e^-\gamma$ channel) as function of $p_T^{\pi^0}$ in Run14 PISA simulation. (b) π^0 mass distribution in $p_T^{\pi^0}$ of 8.5-9GeV. (c) Displacement between the reconstructed γ cluster and the true impact position for photons.

investigation, we found the reconstructed cluster position went wrong because there is a mismatch of the EMCAL geometry used in PISA and in the PHENIX reconstruction code, and we will elaborate more on that in the following sections.

1.2 EMCal geometry in PHENIX

In central arm, 8 sectors of EMCal are installed, 6 of them are of PbSc type and 2 are of PbGl type, shown in Fig. 2. Each sector is like a $4 \times 2m^2$ rectangular wall, and towers are stacked one by one to form a sector. For PbSc sector, there are 72 towers along X in local coordinate, which is along Z (beam) in global coordinate, and 36 towers along Y in local coordinate, which is along ϕ in global coordinate. For PbGl sector, since the tower size is slightly smaller, there are 96 along X in and 48 along Y. When a photon hits a certain tower and create a signal, we need to convert the tower index (iX, iY) to global PHENIX coordinate (x,y,z) to be consistent with other detector subsystems and to extract physics quantities of the detected particle like momentum. Such mapping between the local coordinate (tower index) and global coordinate (cluster position) is what we call as EMCal geometry in this note, which basically describes where towers are located inside a sector and where sectors are located in central arm.

Figure 2: The beam view of PHENIX setup in 2012 data taking period.

The EMCal geometry setting can be categorized to the following 3 classes:

- Radial position and rotational angle for individual sector (sector center along ϕ)
- Number and size of the towers within a sector

- Extra translational offset for a whole sector

Such setting is usually either hard coded in a code, described in a external file, or put to the PHENIX database. We will go through the geometry files used in PHENIX real data analysis and simulation in the following sections.

2 Simulation

2.1 Reconstruction chain

In this section we will describe the full reconstruction chain of simulation used in our Run14 Au+Au direct photon analysis as an example to show at which step the EMCAL geometry is called and where that geometry file is.

Fig. 3 shows the schematic diagram of the reconstruction chain of the single π^0 simulation with Run14 PISA setup. The single π^0 events are generated and then fed to PISA which corresponds to PHENIX detectors installed in GEANT3 framework. In this step, EMCAL geometry is called to build up the detector in PISA, and the file used is called `phnx.par`. After processing through PISA, a raw hits file `PISAEvent.root` is generated. The `PISAEvent.root` is of similar format of PRDF file generated with the real PHENIX detector when taking data, hence the standard PHENIX reconstruction code can be applied to `PISAEvent.root` file to produce the `simDST.root` file, where we have lists of reconstructed tracks, clusters and so on. In this step, EMCAL geometry is used again in the `mEmcClusterizerV0` module, where clusters are formed based on the tower signals. The geometry setting used here is stored in `mEmcGeometryModule` with `kPISA` option. There is another `kReal` option, which is used in the real data reconstruction, and that will be explained in more detail in the next section. After obtaining the `simDST.root` file, our analysis module is applied. This part is highly analysis dependent, and our analysis module is shown just as an example. In our analysis module, we called three modules to adjust the EMCAL energy response in simulation, which are `EmcUnclusterizer`, `EmcTowerScalerSmearer` and `EmcEmbedReclusterizer`. These modules will break down the clusters back to tower signals, adjust the tower energy scale and resolution, and recombine the tower signals to clusters. During this step, more explicitly the reclustering step, the EMCAL geometry is used again with `kPISA` option. At the end, a TTree with $e^+e^-\gamma$ events are generated. If we focus only on the photons, we have both the true impact position (the point where photons first interact with the EMCAL) and the corresponding reconstructed photon cluster position in the output file.

When comparing the reconstructed cluster position to the true impact point, two different EMCAL geometry files are involved. On one hand, the true impact point information comes from PISA, where `phnx.par` is used as EMCAL geometry file. On the other hand, the reconstructed cluster position comes from the reclustering step, where `mEmcGeometryModule` with `kPISA` option is used as EMCAL geometry file. There is a difference between these two geometry files, and that is the key reason for the EMCAL geometry issue we described in section 1.1.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the reconstruction chain in an example simulation.

2.2 mEmcGeometryModule – kPISA

In this section we will introduce how the geometry setting is implemented in mEmcGeometryModule, and compare with the phnx.par file to see the difference.

The source code for mEmcGeometryModule can be found in the following link <https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/offline/packages/emc/mEmcGeometryModule.C?revision=2.29&view=markup>

Fig. 4 shows the geometry setting used for kPISA option. As mentioned in section 1.2, firstly the sector center along ϕ is set for each sector, which corresponds to the second column of emcRA[8][2] in the code. Radial position of each sectors are stored in emcX[8]. Secondly, to determine how the towers are located inside a sector, tower size is given, and 4 constants are defined for tower size along X and Y (local coordinate) for PbSc and PbGl, i.e. TowerXSizeSc, TowerYSizeSc, TowerXSizeGl, TowerYSizeGl. There is no translational offset in this code, so basically 0 for all translational offset.

```
void
mEmcGeometryModule::BuildGeometryPISA()
{
    float deg = M_PI/180.0;
    // Sector dimensions
    int NxSc = 72;
    int NySc = 36;
    int NxGl = 96;
    int NyGl = 48;
    // Tower Size (cm)
    float TowerXSizeSc = 5.542;
    float TowerYSizeSc = 5.542;
    float TowerXSizeGl = 4.1040;
    float TowerYSizeGl = 4.1105;

    // Rotation angles (deg)
    float emcRA[8][2] =
    {
        // SECTOR  ARM(*)  ARM(**)  SECTOR(*)  iS(***)  iS(****)
        {0.0,    22.632}, // W0      1      0      0      0      0
        {0.0,    0.0},   // W1      1      0      1      1      1
        {0.0,   -22.632}, // W2      1      0      2      2      2
        {0.0,   -45.264}, // W3      1      0      3      3      3

        {0.0,   -45.264}, // E3      0      1      3      4      5
        {0.0,   -22.632}, // E2      0      1      2      5      4
        {0.0,    0.0},   // E1      0      1      1      6      7
        {0.0,    22.0}   // E0      0      1      0      7      6
    };
    // (*) = PHENIX convention
    // (**) = EMC Offline convention (e.g. getters/setters of dEmcCalibTower or dEmcClusterLocal)
    // (***) = EMC mEmcGeometryModule convention (this module)
    // (****) = EMC Online convention

    // X position
    float emcX[8] = { 510.0,  510.0,  510.0,  510.0,
                     510.0,  510.0,  543.2,  543.2 };
}
```

Figure 4: Screenshot of kPISA implementation in mEmcGeometryModule.

In comparison, Fig. 5 shows the geometry setting used in PISA, which is phnx.par, next to geometry setting used in reconstruction (clusterization/reclusterization), which is mEmcGeometryModule with kPISA option described above. The source code of phnx.par can be found in the following link <https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/>

[simulation/pisa2000/wrk/phnx.par?revision=1.140&view=markup](https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/simulation/pisa2000/wrk/phnx.par?revision=1.140&view=markup). How the numbers in phnx.par is used by PISA can be found in <https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/simulation/pisa2000/src/emc/emc.f?revision=1.11&view=markup>.

The difference in the geometry settings are either circled out or highlighted. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the sector radial position and sector center in azimuthal direction are slightly different in phnx.par and mEmcGeometry. The tower size of PbSc is smaller in kPISA and there is an additional translational offset implemented in phnx.par.

```

654 $emc_par
655 emc_opt = 3,
656 emc_walls = 8,
657 emc_debug = 1,
658 rpos_emc = 507.7,
659 rpos_emc_add_pbgl = 20.0,
660 emc_deltar_west = 0.0,
661 emc_deltaz_west = 0.0,
662 emc_deltar_east = 0.0,
663 emc_deltaz_east = 0.0,
664 emc_phi_sec1 = -22.152,
665 emc_phi_sec2 = 0.2354,
666 emc_phi_sec3 = 22.785,
667 emc_phi_sec4 = 45.392,
668 emc_phi_sec5 = 45.343,
669 emc_phi_sec6 = 22.900,
670 emc_phi_sec7 = 0.0,
671 emc_phi_sec8 = -22.0,
672 scint_emc_med = 881,
673 fiber_emc_med = 882,
674 pbgl_emc_med = 810,
675 cell_size = 5.58,
676 lead_emc_plates = 65,
677 scint_emc_plates = 66,
678 smskin_emc_thck = 0.05,
679 skin_emc_thck = 0.012,
680 paper_emc_thck = 0.012,
681 fplate_emc_thck = 0.5,
682 hut_emc_thck = 0.2,
683 hut_emc_height = 6.5,
684 bsteel_emc_thck = 0.1,
685 scint_emc_thck = 0.4,
686 lead_emc_thck = 0.15,
687 cage_emc_thck = 1.0,
688 clearance_emc_module = 0.03,
689 clearance_emc_supermodule = 0.08,
690 emc_westarm_deltay = 0.649,
691 emc_westarm_deltaz = 0.816,
692 emc_eastarm_deltay = 0.511,
693 emc_eastarm_deltaz = 0.742,
694 $end

```

```

mEmcGeometryModule::BuildGeometryPISA()
{
    float deg = M_PI/180.0;
    // Sector dimensions
    int NxSc = 72;
    int NySc = 36;
    int NxGl = 96;
    int NyGl = 48;
    // Tower Size (cm)
    float TowerXSizeSc = 5.542;
    float TowerYSizeSc = 5.542;
    float TowerXSizeGl = 4.1040;
    float TowerYSizeGl = 4.1105;

    // Rotation angles (deg)
    float emcRA[8][2] =
    {
        {0.0, 22.632}, // W0
        {0.0, 0.0}, // W1
        {0.0, -22.632}, // W2
        {0.0, -45.264}, // W3
        {0.0, -45.264}, // E3
        {0.0, -22.632}, // E2
        {0.0, 0.0}, // E1
        {0.0, 22.0} // E0
    };
    // (*) = PHENIX convention
    // (**) = EMC Offline convention (e.g. getters/setters of dEmcCalibTower or dEmcClusterLocal)
    // (***) = EMC mEmcGeometryModule convention (this module)
    // (****) = EMC Online convention

    // X position
    float emcX[8] = { 510.0, 510.0, 510.0, 510.0,
                    510.0, 510.0, 543.2, 543.2 };
}

```

Figure 5: Plot on the left shows the screenshot of geometry setting in phnx.par file (EMCal related part), plot on the right shows the screenshot of kPISA implementation in mEmcGeometryModule.

2.3 Diagnostic plots

To crosscheck the effect of such mismatch between the two geometry files used in PISA and reconstruction, one can look at the following two comparisons.

- Comparison between the reconstructed γ cluster position and the true γ impact point extracted from PISA hits file.
- Comparison between the reconstructed γ cluster position and the corresponding track projection position.

Fig. 6 shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point. The offsets along ϕ in each sector is consistent with the difference of sector centers in phnx.par file and mEmcGeometryModule with kPISA option. Fig. 7 shows the emc matching

Figure 6: 2D displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point.

variable as a function single e^\pm track p_T , where $\text{emcd}\phi$ is the difference between the track projection point and associated cluster position along ϕ and $\text{emcd}z$ is the difference between the track projection point and associated cluster position along z . For high p_T e^\pm tracks, $\text{emcd}\phi$ and $\text{emcd}z$ for opposite charge should center around zero because these high p_T tracks do not bend much in the magnetic field. However, it can be seen in Fig. 7 that the e^\pm tracks plateau at a non-zero value, and these non-zero offsets represents the difference of sector centers along ϕ and z direction between the phnx.par file and mEmcGeometryModule with kPISA option.

As shown in section 2.2, there is not only a difference between the sector center position along ϕ and z , but also a radial position/tower size difference between the phnx.par and mEmcGeometryModule with kPISA option. The radial position/tower size difference can be checked via the dependence of the displacement between the true impact point and reconstructed cluster position as a function of ϕ or θ within one sector. If the radial position/tower size are consistent, the displacement should be a constant. If not, the displacement will be larger at one edge and smaller at the other edge of a sector, as shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 7: Top plots show $\text{emcd}\phi$ as a function of single e^\pm track p_T for each sector, bottom plots $\text{emcd}z$ as a function of single e^\pm track p_T for each sector.

Figure 8: The left plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along ϕ as a function of ϕ for each sector. The middle plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along θ as a function of θ for each sector (here θ along x axis are manually moved to avoid overlap of the sectors). The right plot shows schematically why the displacement will be different at the two edges of one sector if there is a mismatch between the radial position or tower size.

2.4 New/Updated geometry setting

To fix the mismatch between the EMCal geometry used in PISA (phnx.par) and the geometry used in reconstruction (mEmcGeometryModule with kPISA option), we updated the settings in kPISA to be consistent with the latest phnx.par file. The new settings for kPISA is summarized in Fig. 9. And the corresponding diagnostic plots are shown in Fig. 10-12. One can see that the reconstructed cluster position is now consistent with the true impact point position/track projection position at high p_T . Also, the displacement is flat along ϕ and θ within one sector, indicating the radial position is correct.

Sim	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.152	-0.2354	-22.785	-45.392	-45.343	-22.9	0	22
Trans y (cm)	0.649	0.649	0.649	0.649	0.511	0.511	0	0
Trans z (cm)	0.816	0.816	0.816	0.816	0.742	0.742	0	0
Tsize x (cm)	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	4.104	4.104
Tsize y (cm)	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	4.104	4.104
R pos (cm)	511.2	511.2	511.2	511.2	511.2	511.2	541.2	541.2

Figure 9: Geometry settings in the updated mEmcGeometryModule with kPISA option.

Figure 10: 2D displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point.

Figure 11: Top plots show $emcd\phi$ as a function of single e^\pm track p_T for each sector, bottom plots show $emcdz$ as a function of single e^\pm track p_T for each sector.

Figure 12: The left plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along ϕ as a function of ϕ for each sector. The right plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along θ as a function of θ for each sector (here θ along x axis are manually moved to avoid overlap of the sectors).

3 Real data

In this section, we will follow a similar story line as in the simulation section to go through the previous geometry setting used in real data and how it can be improved.

3.1 Reconstruction chain

In this section, we will describe the reconstruction chain of real data, and still taking Run14 Au+Au direct photon analysis as an example to show at which step the EMCal geometry is called and where that geometry file is.

Fig. 13 shows the schematic diagram of the reconstruction chain of real data. Each event corresponds to a real collision, and the detector response of the particles in acceptance are saved in raw data file – PRDF file. These PRDF files then go through the production procedure, where the standard PHENIX reconstruction code are applied to produce DST.root file. During the production, depending if the data is taken before or after 2010, either lists of clusters are saved or lists of calibrated towers are saved. In the case of Run14 Au+Au at 200GeV data set, lists of calibrated towers are saved and clusterization are actually performed during the recalibration. After production, we run recalibrators and our analysis module on the DST files. One of the recalibrators – ReadbackCompactPWG will call EmcClusterContainerResurrector module, where clusterization is done and lists of reconstructed clusters are formed based on tower signals and saved in emcClusterContainer. In this clusterization step, EMCal geometry is used, and the corresponding geometry settings are stored in mEmcGeometryModule with kReal option. At the end, in our direct photon analysis, a TTree of $e^+e^-\gamma$ events are generated similarly to the simulation case. However, one major difference from the simulation is we no longer have the true information. Therefore, in real data, we mainly use the track projection position as a reference to check if the EMCal geometry is off or not with respect to the tracking detector (i.e. Drift Chamber).

Figure 13: Schematic diagram of the reconstruction chain in Run14 Au+Au at 200GeV data set.

3.2 mEmcGeometryModule – kReal

Fig. 14 shows how the EMCAL geometry is implemented in mEmcGeometryModule for kReal option. It reads the rotation matrix and translation vector from the data base. The rational angles (sector center along ϕ), radial position, tower sizes and extra translational offset can be extracted from the rotation matrix and translation vector. The extracted numbers are shown in Fig. 15.

```
void
mEmcGeometryModule::BuildGeometry()
{
    readFromDB();

    // loop over EMCAL Sectors
    for (int is = 0; is<MAX_SECTORS; is++){
        // create the inverse matrices and vectors after reading from DB
        // this is just to make sure that the inverse corresponds to the direct,
        // since it is possible to write into DB just one or the other
        PHFrame local;
        PHFrame global= MatrixAndVector2frames(local,emcrm[is],emctr[is]);
        frames2MatrixAndVector(global,local,invemcrm[is],invemctr[is]);
    }
}

void mEmcGeometryModule::readFromDB()
{
    // create a data manager
    emcGeometry geom;
    emcDataManager *dm = emcDataManager::GetInstance();

    geom.SetSource(emcDBMS::get());

    PHTimeStamp now;
    bool ok = dm->Read(geom,now,1);
    if(!ok){
        BuildGeometryPISA();
    }
    else{
        assert(MAX_SECTORS==geom.NumberOfSectors());
        for(int is = 0; is <MAX_SECTORS; is ++){
            emcrm[is] = geom.Sector(is).RotationMatrix();
            emctr[is] = geom.Sector(is).TranslationVector();
            nx[is] = geom.Sector(is).nx();
            ny[is] = geom.Sector(is).ny();
            tower_xsize[is] = geom.Sector(is).Tower_xSize();
            tower_ysize[is] = geom.Sector(is).Tower_ySize();
        }
        printf("<I> mEmcGeometryModule: REAL Geometry Initialized\n");
    }
}
```

Figure 14: Screenshot of kReal implementation in mEmcGeometryModule.

At this point we do not have a file documenting where the EMCAL detector sits during the data taking period, therefore we cannot compare the geometry file used in the reconstruction to where the detector is directly. However, we can still look the displacement between the the

Data	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.151	-0.302	-22.784	-45.390	-45.341	-22.899	-0.154	22.139
Trans y (cm)	-0.451	-0.172	0.009	-0.322	-0.810	-0.085	1.776	0.138
Trans z (cm)	1.114	0.899	1.200	1.393	0.890	-0.128	1.195	1.049
Tsize x (cm)	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	4.092	4.092
Tsize y (cm)	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	4.106	4.106
R pos (cm)	506.991	507.197	507.124	507.360	507.982	507.489	540.115	539.057

Figure 15: Geometry settings in the mEmcGeometryModule with kReal option.

track projection position and reconstructed cluster position to judge if the EMCal geometry used in reconstruction is off or not with respect to the Drift Chamber. In particular, one can choose zero field runs to avoid the bending of the track so that the tracking can serve as a good reference no matter the track is of low p_T or high p_T . Fig. 16 shows the displacement between the track projection point and reconstructed cluster position as a function of ϕ or θ within one sector using zero field runs. Firstly, it can be seen that the sector center is off in both ϕ and z direction, and that is why the spread of $\text{emcd}\phi$ and emcdz for each sector is not centered around zero. Secondly, there is a dependence of $\text{emcd}\phi$ on ϕ within one sector, similar behavior is also observed for emcdz . That indicates the radial position or the tower sizes used in the reconstruction are not matching the real detector case.

Figure 16: The left plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along ϕ as a function of ϕ for each sector. The right plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along θ as a function of θ for each sector (here θ along x axis are manually moved to avoid overlap of the sectors).

3.3 New/Updated geometry setting

To fix the mismatch between the real EMCAL geometry and the geometry used in reconstruction, we tuned the radial position, translational offset and tower size along x (local coordinate) for PbGl sectors of the geometry setting used in reconstruction, and the new setting can be found in Fig. 17. With the new setting, the displacement between the track projection point and reconstructed cluster position is shown in Fig. 18. From Fig. 18 we can see that now the sector center are sitting are the correct place, although there might still be some mismatch either in radial position or tower size. However, the residual difference is rather small and the effect should be much smaller compare to other systematics of our analysis.

Data	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.151	-0.302	-22.784	-45.390	-45.341	-22.899	-0.154	22.139
Trans y (cm)	1.249	1.128	1.109	-0.222	1.290	0.715	2.576	0.338
Trans z (cm)	-0.486	-0.901	-0.400	-0.407	1.290	0.722	1.595	1.849
Tsize x (cm)	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	4.116	4.116
Tsize y (cm)	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	4.106	4.106
R pos (cm)	508.991	509.197	509.124	509.360	509.982	508.489	536.115	536.057

Figure 17: Geometry settings in the updated mEmcGeometryModule with kReal option.

Figure 18: The left plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along ϕ as a function of ϕ for each sector. The right plot shows the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along θ as a function of θ for each sector (here θ along x axis are manually moved to avoid overlap of the sectors).